

REVIEW PAPER ON UNIT SOLID DOSAGE FORMS-TABLET

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ABSTRACT

Tablets are the unit solid dosage form which contains medicament or medicaments, drug or drugs with or without excipients & prepared by a molding or compression. The most common way of drug administration is a tablets which are taken by orally. Tablets are a popular dosage form because of their advantages & easiest for a administration as well as manufacturing as compared to other dosage forms. There are a several categories of tablets are available in the market according to the patient Requirement a pharmacist provide an effective drug to the particular patient. There are different brands are available in the market for a same drug which contain a same API with excipients & having same therapeutic action.

KEYWORDS: Tablet, Solid unit dosage form, API, therapeutic effect.

INTRODUCTION

For getting a proper or accurate treatment of any disease or disorder, a registered medical practitioner prescribes various Pharmaceutical dosage forms including tablets, pills, capsules, creams, ointments, suppositories, sprays, syrups and injectables. To achieve proper treatment or quick recovery, tablets are popularly used dosage forms manufactured by dry granulation, wet granulation or direct compression or molding, containing medicaments with/without suitable diluents.

According to its use or route of administration and amount of medicaments used, tablets are

different in shape, size, weight and hardness. They also vary in hardness and thickness, disintegration, dissolving time and their therapeutic action. Various forms of tablets are available and their popularity is increasing day by day because of their advantages.

Advantages

Accurate dose

Each table contains a uniform & fixed amount of drug for its proper dosing & reducing chance of overdosing.

Easy to handle & carry

Tablets are easy to handle & carry for the patient because of light in weight, small & portable

Good stability

Because of its less moisture & less prone to microbial they are more stable than liquid dosage forms.

Mask unpleasant test & odor

Coating materials or additives can cove bitter test or unpleasant odors of drugs, improve patient compliance.

Economical

It it economical for patient because of low cost as manufacturer because of its simple production & packaging process.

Easy identification

Tablets are easy to identify for children, Adults as well as aging person because of its various shapes, colors & identifying marks or logos.

Controlled or sustained release possible

Some types of coating of tables or formulation can make tablets release drug slowly over time, reducing dosing frequency.

Long self-life

Tablets are protected from environmental factors & dried well so they remain stable for long periods.

Disadvantages**Not suitable for all drugs**

Some drugs have poor compressibility or hard in nature so they cannot be compress into tablets.

Slow onset of action

Tablets have to disintegrate & dissolve before absorption So they have slow action as compared to liquid or injection.

Difficult for children & elderly

Children & adults or older have difficulty or trouble to swallowing a tablets so they have difficulty to take tablets.

Not suitable for large doses

If a drug required large dose the tablet may become too big to swallow easily.

Irritation to stomach: Some drugs cause irritation or ulceration in the stomach lining when taken orally in the form of tablet.

Less bioavailability

After administration tablets are first disintegrate & dissolve then absorbed into bloodstream, which can reduce its bioavailability as compared to IV route.

Types of tablets

- Oral tablet
- Compressed tablet
- Sugar coated tablet
- Film coated tablet
- Chewable tablet
- Enteric coated tablet
- Buccal tablets
- Sublingual tablets
- Troches
- Slow release tablet
- Modified release tablet

Tablets for oral administration (Oral tablets)

Compressed tablet: - These tablets are made by compression of granules; do not have a coating (uncoated).

Sugar coated tablet: - These are compressed tablets coated with a sugar (Glucose) layer for a protection as well as to mask a better taste or to provide sweet taste.

Film coated tablet: - Film coated tablets are compressed tablets coated with a thin polymer film to improve appearance, protect drug & control release of drug.

Chewable tablet: - These are solid oral dosage forms, which are large & hard, difficult to swallow. These are placed in the mouth, chewed & swallowed, not swallowed whole. Especially useful for children, elderly who cannot swallow proper tablets.

Enteric coated: - These tablets are coated with acid resistant substance that does not dissolve in the acidic pH of the stomach but dissolve's only in the alkaline pH of the intestine.

Buccal tablets: - Buccal tablets are small, flat, tablets formulated to be placed between the gum & the cheek, where they slowly dissolve & provide systemic or local drug action.

Sublingual tablets: Sublingual tablets are placed under the tongue & allowed to dissolve & it absorbs due to sublingual route. These are 100% absorbed in bloodstream.

Effervescent tablets: These are solid oral dosage forms containing sodium bicarbonate & an organic acid in addition to drug substance. Before use these are dissolved into water after taking & result in carbon dioxide (CO₂) release & effervescence or bubbling are produced. Substance which are allowed to dissolve in the mouth. They are mainly used for cold & sore throat.

Slow release tablets: These tablets are coated with a special type of coating which release a drug slowly over an extended period, instead of releasing it all at once. These are administered less frequently.

Modified release tablets: These tablets are release a drug with delay after its administration or for prolonged period of time.

Tablets for vaginal administration

These tablets are intended to be inserted into the vagina.

Where they dissolve or disintegrated to release the medication locally which are readily soluble into blood stream.

Tablets for implantation

Tablet = API+Excipient

API(active pharmaceutical ingredients)

It is the biologically active chemical substance in a tablets or in a pharmaceutical dosage form used for producing the intended therapeutic effect.

Properties of API used in tables

1. Having a good flowaility.
2. Compressibility
3. Thermal and chemical stability
4. Non hygroscopic
5. Good solubility
6. Appropriate partial size
7. Compatible with excipients

Sources of API**Chemical synthetic source**

Paracetamol, diclofenac

Plant source.

Example Atropine, Digoxin

Animal source

Example Insulin - pancreas of pig or cow, lanolin - sheep wool

Microbial/fermentation source Example penicillin - penicillium fungus, vit B12-fermentation

Mineral source

Example magnesium hydroxide, Karolin

Marin source

Example Agar, Omega -3-fatty acids

Semi synthetic source

Example Amoxicillin, Hydrocortisone

Excipients

Excipients are commonly used in tablets having a different function in it. They are inactive

substances added to a dosage form along with the active pharmaceutical ingredient. They do not have therapeutic action. They are essentially added to help in the formulation of excipients and the formulations.

Functions of excipients

Binders

Binders help in holding the particles together to form a compact tablet. They provide mechanical strength. Examples: Starch, cellulose derivative.

Diluents

In case of a drug or API that is very small, diluents are used to increase the bulk of tablets. They ensure uniform size, weight, and content. Examples: Lactose, manifold.

Lubricants

Lubricants do not have therapeutic effect but are added in tablets to reduce friction between tablet material and machine dies during compression. Examples: Stearic acid, talc.

Preservatives

Preservatives are used to prevent microbial growth in liquid and semisolid formulations. Example: Sodium benzoate.

Sweetening agents

Sweetening agents are used to mask a bitter taste and improve palatability of oral formulations. They provide a sweet taste. Examples: Sucrose, sorbitol.

Flavoring agents

Flavoring agents are used to improve the flavor of the formulation. Examples: Orange, vanilla.

Coloring agents

Coloring agents give color to the tablets for identification and appearance.

Methods of tablet preparation

Wet granulation

Dry granulation

Direct compression method

Wet Granulation Method

Wet granulation is the most commonly used and oldest method of tablet preparation. The powdered and mixed tablet ingredients are converted into a moist, coherent mass and then converted into granules before compression into tablets.

The most essential and careful steps during the preparation of tablets are weighing, mixing, granulation, screening the damp mass, drying, dry screening, lubrication and then finally compression of the material.

This method is a time-consuming method. The process involves the blending and mixing of active ingredients, diluents and disintegrates. The mixed material is then sifted through a screen of suitable mesh to remove or break the lumps by adding and mixing with the binder solution the sifted material is converted into a damp mass. The damp mass is forced through 6-8 mesh screens for granulation. Through the oven the weight granules are dried partials may agglomerated and forms lump and therefore screening operation is often required after drying. Then in the dried granules added the remaining quantity of disinter grant and lubricant. Then finally the granules are compressed into tablets.

Dry granulation is a method

Dry granulation is a method of tablet preparation in which granules are made without using any liquid binder.

This method is mainly used for drugs that are sensitive to moisture or heat, because no wetting or drying steps are involved. In dry granulation, the required quantities of drug, diluent, and other excipients are first accurately weighed and mixed in dry form. The mixed powder is then compressed into a large, dense mass, which can be done either by slugging, where the powder is compressed into large tablets called slugs, or by roller compaction, where the powder is squeezed between two rollers to form sheets or ribbons. The compressed mass is then broken and milled to produce granules of suitable size. These granules are passed through sieves to obtain uniform-sized granules, while oversized pieces are re-milled and fine powder may be recycled. After sieving, a lubricant such as magnesium stearate is added to improve flow and prevent sticking during compression. Finally, the lubricated granules are fed into a tablet compression machine to produce the finished tablets. This method provides good flow and compressibility to powders and is ideal when the drug cannot tolerate wet granulation.

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Direct Compression Method

Direct compression is the simplest and most rapid method of tablet manufacturing because the tablets are made directly from the powder blend, without any granulation step. In this method, all the required ingredients such as the drug, diluent, disintegrant, gliding, and lubricant are accurately weighed and thoroughly mixed to obtain a uniform powder mixture. The powders used must have good flow properties.

And excellent compressibility, which is why special directly compressible excipients like microcrystalline cellulose (MCC), spray-dried lactose, and calcium phosphate are commonly used. After uniform mixing, the powder blend is directly fed into a tablet compression machine, where it is compressed into tablets with the desired hardness and size. Since no wetting, drying, or granulation is involved, direct compression is fast, economical, and ideal for heat- or moisture-sensitive drugs. However, the method requires powders with good flow and uniformity; otherwise, problems like poor content uniformity or weight variation may occur.

Overall, direct compression is a clean, simple, and efficient technique used widely for tablets whenever suitable excipients and drug properties allow it.

CONCLUSION

Tablets are one of the most important and commonly used dosage forms in the field of medicine. They are popular because they are easy to use, easy to carry, affordable, and provide an accurate amount of medicine in every dose. Tablets are made by combining the active drug with different excipients that help in binding, disintegration, lubrication, taste

masking, and improving the overall quality of the tablet. This ensures that patients receive the right dose in a safe, effective, and easy-to-swallow form.

There are many different types of tablets available, such as sugar-coated, film-coated, chewable, enteric-coated, buccal, sublingual, effervescent, slow-release, and modified-release tablets. Each type is designed for a specific purpose—for example, to protect the drug, improve taste, release the drug slowly, or allow rapid absorption. This variety helps Doctors and pharmacists choose the most suitable tablet for each patient based on their needs and medical conditions.

Tablet preparation methods like wet granulation, dry granulation, and direct compression allow manufacturers to make tablets with proper strength, stability, and uniformity. These methods also make tablets suitable for different types of drugs, including those that are sensitive to heat or moisture. Although tablets also have some disadvantages, such as difficulty in swallowing for children and elderly patients, slower onset of action, and unsuitability for large doses, they still remain the most widely accepted dosage form.

Overall, tablets play a major role in delivering medicines effectively. Their stability, long shelf-life, low cost, and ease of administration make them the preferred choice in healthcare. As pharmaceutical science continues to advance, tablet formulations will continue to improve, offering even better therapeutic outcomes and greater patient comfort.

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